

QUICK FIX MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: *This app helps people whose cars break down at strange hours. When someone's vehicle breaks down while travelling, they can contact for help using this app. Client logs into app to communicate location and car problem with data owner. By sharing the client's vehicle's location, trouble, and other details, the data owner helps the client. If we can't help them immediately, we offer to rent them a car. We'll return their car in two to three days, take payment, and drive away.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Smartphone apps boost auto repair. End consumers get speed, convenience, and performance. Handbooks aren't as helpful as vehicle apps while driving. This programme helps users who have problems locating help when their vehicle breaks down or runs out of gasoline at unusual times or on city outskirts. First, customers open and connect to this app with their registered username and password. When they select "Ask Help," the app asks for their live location and the problem with their vehicle. Then, the data owner transmits the case to the nearest working mechanic based on the client's location.

For the mechanic's safety, the data owner must see if he's travelling in the right path. After contacting the client, both of their locations should be on; if one is off, we'll react immediately. If he can't fix it in time, he must explain why. If a mechanic cannot help a client out, for example, an internal repair in their vehicle at night, then the mechanic offers the client a vehicle on behalf from this app so they can reach their destination safely. The client's vehicle goes with the mechanic, and the client will get a spontaneous update of when the vehicle will arrive. After getting repaired, our staff will return with the client's rental vehicle and give them the whole bill. This is a useful app.

II. RELATED WORK

Smartphone technology isn't for complacent thinkers, but for those who seek opportunities to use it. Smartphones are affecting our approach, goals, and routines, even when driving. Many car-related apps appeared, which are different from TOOL and Hire. Some apps help automobile owners find a technician. Since it's difficult to trust the reputation of local Copyrights @Muk Publications

mechanics and choose among repair quotes, the app does it for you, but only when it's urgent. These apps are helpful for roadside car maintenance, service, and repair. Easy-to-use, they all offer distinct services and features and can add several vehicles based on maintenance needs.

Car maintenance apps are now available. Car maintenance takes time, money, and effort. Finding cheap gas or remembering when to get an oil change might be difficult. When car upkeep becomes burdensome, many owners overpay for gas or skip tune-ups. Maintaining your car, however inconvenient, is crucial. Failing to maintain your car pushes you to pay for expensive repairs or a new car sooner than you should.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

1. Repair does the work for you and comes up with a rough estimate for your service based on average costs in your area. You can head to your local dealership or mechanic with that number in mind. If the price they offer is much higher than Repair Pal's estimate, you can recognize the rip-off immediately and take your business somewhere that offers a fairer price.
2. If you have trouble remembering when it's time to take your car in for a tune-up, Car Minder is a resource you need. This app lets you know when you need to schedule maintenance based on one-time information you input directly from your car's owner's manual. It also allows you to log a history of all service on your car, so you can keep track of expenses for major repairs as well as scheduled maintenance.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Our application helps the people who has a vehicle breakdown at outside of the city or he is in a position where there is no one to help .By using this application the user can call for help by filling a details form about the type and problem of the vehicle and we will be given a number in application that he can send his live location of the area. By understanding the situation of the user, our data owner shares the live location of the client to the nearby mechanic who is available, experts will go and help with the problem of their vehicles. Mechanic reaches the client in a slotted time and his location should not be off until his work was done.

If there is any possibility that we cannot repair it on the spot then the user can request for us an vehicle for rent which we will be providing, then user can reach his destination safely and we will be returning there vehicle after it got repaired and updates has been given to the client therefore he can know what’s going on with his vehicle. The clients vehicles can be either two wheeler or four wheeler and can be three wheeler we can help with and the repair of the vehicle can be completed and delivered to the client within a week.

Then client can know what the problem with the vehicle what repair has done and check it whether it is repaired or not if the vehicle got repaired again within a week client can consult us or if client find that something is wrong with his vehicle then he/she can consult us to discuss the problem. This application mostly help out women and female teenagers, We can help them out in many situations based on the profile of the client if it was a lady then our lady mechanic along with a male will reach out the client in time.

V. ARCHITECTURE

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Data Owner

Data owner has access to database .He can verify the user is authenticate user or not and always work with the system if there are emergency services to react with. And Data owner is the one who manages the whole system , Data owner checks the details of the vehicle, user details and message posted by the client.

He carries the information from the client to the mechanic by getting live location from the client.so, that he can share the location and problem of the vehicle by contacting the mechanic to the nearby location of the client. Data owner manages the mechanics who are available at work and get in touch with active one.

Mechanic

Mechanic works when he gets a call from the data owner or maintainer and gets into the duty. Mechanic reaches the client easily by following the location of the client. So that the mechanic helps them on the spot if it is an external fault like tier puncturing, engine problem etc.

It’s not easy for a mechanic to find out the internal engine problem, it makes too difficult if it is nightfall. So, then he provides an offer for a client which is another helpful process provided by this application. He convinces the client to take our vehicle that we will drive their vehicle to their own home after we repair it and other paperwork will be done on the spot by the mechanic.

Client

Client is an important agent with whom we run the application. At first , the client installs the application in his mobile and register’s in the application by submitting his details that are given ,

for user's safety we are providing them username and password to login into the app.

Client can ask help if there is any problem with his vehicle at any odd time by sharing his problem via message and by sharing his live location. Mechanics who are nearby will reach him/her within a short period of time. Atlast, after getting his vehicle ready they can have a safe journey.

VI. CONCLUSION

We propose a new scheme for making the automobile repairs can be done at any time and made things easy for people in such vehicle breakdown cases and provides employment for many mechanical and IT students. We are providing safety from this app for people that they don't have to wait for someone to come and help them at late nights or they don't have ask lift for unknown strangers.

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